

LONG-TERM THEORETICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS OF LIMIT STATES OF STEEL-CONCRETE COMPOSITE BEAMS FOR STRUCTURAL USE

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SUMMARY: This paper describes a theoretical and experimental analysis model which permits the evaluation of the long duration flexural and nonlinear creep characteristics of cracked and non-cracked prestressed steel-concrete composite beams for structural use. Some large-scale test data and once evaluated strength parameters have been successfully used to provide encouraging support for the theoretical predictions of the stress redistributions and the long-term ultimate flexural loads in the planning phase. The research object in this present paper relates to prestressed steel-concrete composite beams of I and II categories of resistance to cracking, not only as the most spreaded used prefabricated structural elements, but also like the most convenient models for theoretical and experimental studies, which can permit to widely and reliably reveal their positive effect and generalize it to more complicated type of structural elements. The consideration of this said positive effect can be able to ensure the economy of steel reinforcement up to 15 %.

KEYWORDS:matrix shrinkage strains, shear strains, stress losses, nonlinear strain function, matrix creep ageing theory, Navier's hypothesis, Hooke's law, principle of Juravsky.

INTRODUCTION

Today many negative factors like ageing, increased loads, exposure to aggressive environmental factors of building steel-concrete composite structures have resulted in their progressive deterioration. That's why the need of long-term theoretical and experimental analysis of limit states of these said building structures at planing phase is so actual that many research foundations with their members are involved in different focus areas of civil engineering, but few original research works concerning the positive effects of time-dependent stress redistribution in these said composite members have been conducted.

The theoretical part of this study relates to the details of a unified design procedure for analytical prediction of various durability and quality characteristics of boubly reinforced and prestressed steel-concrete composite beams for structural use, exposed to long-term service loads. This analytical procedure is aimed to predict the quality, stiffness, strength and durability

at the planning phase, the nonlinear creep and progressive cracking behaviour of these said composite members. For structural and crack-growth predictions, the well-known virtual work principles have been used to estimate (a) transient strains due to matrix creep and shrinkage, (b) the resulting time-dependent stress redistributions, as well as (c) displacement variations in doubly reinforced and prestressed composite members. The matrix shear stresses have been evaluated by the well-known principle of Juravsky. The finite-difference method based on the displacement formulation has been successfully used to solve the systems of nonlinear equilibrium differential equations.

The need to validate the results, required detailed planning of series of full-scale controlled experiments which permitted the evaluations said at above points (a) - (c) in addition to (d) calibrating the parameters likely to enable the estimation of the time-dependent prestressing losses, (e) predicting the section stiffness and strength by determining the long term flexural and nonlinear creep capacity of the cracked and uncracked sections and hence, (f) devising a definition for structural durability and integrity, with regards to matrix stress-strain relationship under long-term service loads.

THEORETICAL ANALYSIS

The nonlinear equation of the concrete matrix creep ageing theory reflects the correlation between the stress $\sigma_b(t)$ and the strain $\varepsilon_b(\tau)$ by its modulus of elasticity $E_b(\tau)$, the nonlinear strain function $f[\varepsilon_b(\tau)] = \varepsilon_b(\tau) + \beta(\tau) \varepsilon_b^2(\tau)$, where the coefficient of nonlinearity $\beta(\tau) = E_0 \beta_0 / [1 + k \varphi(\tau)]^2$, (β_0 and k once determined by experimental graphics have been successfully used like constant test data), and the relaxation measure $r(t, \tau)$ which has been formulated by the matrix creep characteristic φ like $r(t, \tau) = E_0 \{ 1 - e^{-[\varphi(t) - \varphi(\tau)]} \}$:

$$\sigma_b(t) = \varepsilon_b(t_0) E_b(t_0) - f[\varepsilon_b(t_0)] r(t, t_0) + \int_{t_0}^t \{ (d\varepsilon_b(\tau) / d\tau) E_b(\tau) - (d f [\varepsilon_b(\tau)] / d\tau) r(t, \tau) \} d\tau, \quad (1)$$

where t - loading duration; τ - concrete age; t_0 - loading beginning moment.

In the modified ageing theory, accepted like work theory with a constant matrix modulus of elasticity E_0 , the correlation (1) acquires the following form:

$$\sigma_b(\varphi) = E_0 \{ \varepsilon_b(\varphi) - e^{-\varphi} \int f[\varepsilon_b(\varphi)] e^{\varphi} d\varphi \}. \quad (2)$$

By deriving (2) relatively to φ , taking into account the matrix shrinkage strain $\varepsilon_{sh}(\varphi)$, we have obtained:

$$\sigma_b + \sigma_b = E_0 [\varepsilon_b - \varepsilon_{sh} - \beta (\varepsilon_b - \varepsilon_{sh})^2]. \quad (3)$$

Here and in the next formulas the functions' derivatives have been presented by points.

Then, by examining the element of the steel-concrete composite beam, reinforced by many reinforcement $e = 1, 2, \dots, s$ rows, with cracked and uncracked sections, we have proceeded from the condition of the equation (3), the Navier's hypothesis for the concrete matrix:

$$\varepsilon_b = \varepsilon + \mathfrak{K} z, \quad (4)$$

and for the e -th steel reinforcement row:

$$\varepsilon_e = \varepsilon + \mathfrak{K} z_e, \quad (5)$$

and the Hooke's law for the e -th steel reinforcement row:

$$\sigma_e = E_e \varepsilon_e, \quad (6)$$

where z and z_e - conformably distances from the composite beam element axis to a certain concrete matrix layer, and to the e -th reinforcement row;

$\sigma_e, \varepsilon_e, E_e$ - stress, strain and modulus of elasticity of the e -th reinforcement row;

ε - shortening strain; \mathfrak{K} - flexural curvature of the member element.

Displacements in the composite element Δ have been evaluated, using the well known principle of virtual displacements:

$$\Delta = \int (M_1 \mathfrak{K} + N_1 \varepsilon)_i dx, \quad (7)$$

where $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ - number of homogeneous elements with length l_i ;

M_1 and N_1 - efforts from the generalized force unit, applied at the place and to the direction of the unknown displacement; x - ordinate of the composite beam element section in length.

Joint deformation conditions

Because of the joint deformations of the concrete matrix and the reinforcement at the same time, the arrangement of (5) into (6) gives:

$$\sigma_e = E_e (\varepsilon + \mathfrak{K} z_e). \quad (8)$$

By taking into account the fact that the shrinkage strain ε_{sh} is independent of z , and by arranging (4) into (3) we obtained:

$$\sigma_b + \sigma_b = E_0 [\varepsilon - \varepsilon_{sh} + \mathfrak{K} z - \beta (\varepsilon - \varepsilon_{sh} + \mathfrak{K} z)^2]. \quad (9)$$

Equilibrium conditions

The normal stress components and the displacements of the composite beam element have been evaluated by using strain components \mathfrak{K} and ε , which represent the principal functions of the long-term flexural theory. For the determination of the said \mathfrak{K} and ε , have been used the equilibrium conditions:

$$M = M_b + M_e = M_b + M_s = \int \sigma_b z dA_b + \sum \sigma_e A_e z_e; \quad (10)$$

$$N = N_b + N_e = N_b + N_s = \int \sigma_b dA_b + \sum \sigma_e A_e, \quad (11)$$

where A_b and A_e - sections areas of principal effective concrete layer, and of e -th reinforcement row; M and N - flexural moment and compressive force; s - total number of rows.

The combined consideration of (10), (9), (8), and then of (11), (9), (8), conformably lead to the following differential equations, relatively to \mathfrak{K} and ε :

$$M' + \mathfrak{K}^* = \lambda \mathfrak{K} + \eta (\varepsilon + \varepsilon_{sh}) - \beta [v \mathfrak{K}^2 + 2(1 - \lambda) \mathfrak{K} (\varepsilon - \varepsilon_{sh}) - \eta (\varepsilon - \varepsilon_{sh})^2]; \quad (12)$$

$$N' + \varepsilon^* = \mu \varepsilon + i^2 \eta \mathfrak{K} - (1 - \mu) \varepsilon_{sh} - \beta [(1 - \mu) (\varepsilon - \varepsilon_{sh})^2 - 2i^2 \eta \mathfrak{K} (\varepsilon - \varepsilon_{sh}) + i^2 (1 - \lambda) \mathfrak{K}^2], \quad (13)$$

where $\mathfrak{K}^* = M / (E_0 \mathfrak{I}_{red})$; $\varepsilon^* = N / (E_0 A_{red})$; $v = I_b / \mathfrak{I}_{red}$; $A_{red} = A_b + A_{s,red}$; $i^2 = \mathfrak{I}_{red} / A_{red}$;

$$S_{red} = S_b + S_{s,red} = 0 ; \mu = A_{s,red}/A_{red} ; \mathfrak{S}_{red} = \mathfrak{S}_b + \mathfrak{S}_{s,red} ; \lambda = \mathfrak{S}_{s,red} / \mathfrak{S}_{red} ; \eta = S_{s,red} / \mathfrak{S}_{red}.$$

In mechanics of reinforced concrete structures I_b represents the inertia moment of 3-th order. Formulas for its evaluation have been explicitly presented in [1, 2, 4]. Here and in the next formulas the elastic strain and stress components are indicated with stars. Here also:

$$S_b = \int z dA_b ; \mathfrak{S}_b = \int z^2 dA_b ; I_b = \int z^3 dA_b - \text{conformably statical moment, usual inertia}$$

moment and inertia moment of 3-th order, of the principal effective concrete matrix layer, relatively to the axis passing by the reduced section center of the composite member.

Then, the combined consideration of (12), (13) and (9) leads to the following differential equation, relatively to σ_b and ε_{sh} :

$$, \quad (14)$$

where

$$. \quad (15)$$

The differential equations (12), (13) and (14) have been resolved by using the finite difference method [1, 2, 4]. The essence of this simple and suitable method consists of the fact that the variable φ has been divided into $j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, n$ equal parts (Fig. 1) with step h . Thus, the derivate of the function $F(\varphi)$ at settled points has been evaluated by following formula:

$$= (F_{j+1} - F_j)/h. \quad (16)$$

In that way, by using (16), the differential equations have been changed into simple recurrent algebraic formylas by which it is easy to determinate the stresses and strains in any e -th reinforcement row, the stresses and strains in the concrete matrix at any level of the ordinate z , and the beam displacements Δ :

$$; \quad (17)$$

$$; \quad (18)$$

$$; \quad (19)$$

$$; \quad (20)$$

$$; \quad ; \quad . \quad (21), (22), (23)$$

Have been used the initial values of the functions relatively to $\varphi = 0$: $M(0) = M_0$; $N(0) = N_0$;

$$= \mathfrak{R}_0 = M_0/(E_0 \mathfrak{S}_{red}) ; \quad = \varepsilon_0 = N_0/(E_0 \mathfrak{S}_{red}); \quad = \sigma_{e0} = E_e(\varepsilon_0 + \mathfrak{R}_0 z_e); \quad = \sigma_{b0} = E_0(\varepsilon_0 + \mathfrak{R}_0 z).$$

The matrix shear stresses have been evaluated by the well-known principle of Juravsky. Analogically to the case of ancracked beams, have been evaluated new geometrical characteristics of the cracked sections and by using the finite difference method, have been determinated the exponents of limit states of cracked composite members [1,2,4].

Fig. 1: a) To the explanation of the finite difference method; b) Stress-strain state of a certain uncracked composite beam element, and its section.

Stress redistribution, Prestressing losses and proper stresses

Before the pressing out of the element by prestressing efforts, in the e-th reinforcement row has been acted the initial controlled stress $\sigma_{e, \text{contr.}}$, without first stress losses, independent of the deformation properties of the concrete matrix [1, 2, 4].

At the moment of the pressing out, taken like the beginning of time-dependent counting out, in the reinforcement and the matrix were springing up elastoinstantaneous increases of stresses correspondingly σ_{e0} and $\sigma_{b0}(z_e)$, where z_e - distance from the element center of the reduced section to the axis of the e-th reinforcement row. At the time moment τ they were changing and their current value became equal to $\sigma_e(\tau)$ and $\sigma_b(z_e, \tau)$, with the fact that stresses in the reinforcement were increasing, but in the concrete matrix they were reducing. After the moment of the pressing out the said initial controlled stresses $\sigma_{e, \text{contr.}}$ have become equal to:

$$\sigma_{e, \text{contr.}} - \sigma_e(\tau). \quad (24)$$

According to Ukraine Codes of reinforced concrete structures 1.03.01-84 [3], stress losses due to the concrete matrix shrinkage and creep in a certain e-th reinforcement row concern that part of stresses, which cannot supply themselves with the action of a certain effort P, applied with an eccentricity e_{0P} and which can annullify the stresses developed in the concrete matrix $\sigma_b(z_e, \tau)$ at the level of the same reinforcement row, at the design moment of the composite beams. In that way, the stresses $\sigma_b(z_e, \tau)$ can be provoked by the reinforcement prestressing efforts, the matrix shrinkage, the composite beams weight and the long term service loads on the beams.

At the moment t, as the long term service loads were acting on the beams (fig. 2, a), so the application of these said loads has changed stresses in the matrix and in the reinforcement to elastoinstantaneous quantities conformably $\sigma_e(t)$ and $\sigma_b(z_e, t)$, and the long duration of these said loads can contribute to the fact that, stresses in the reinforcement have been increased, but in the matrix these stresses have been reduced, and just this positive effect can contribute to the durability and to the increase of the efficiency of the use of these said composite beams. Then the beam element has been unloaded and the stresses have been reduced (fig. 2, b).

By applying to the element, the conditional effort P with an eccentricity e_{0P} at a certain moment t_1 for the purpose to reduce the developed stresses $\sigma_b(z_e, t_1)$ to zero (fig. 2, c), we have changed the stresses in the reinforcement to a certain quantity: $\alpha_e(t_1) \sigma_b(z_e, t_1)$, where $\alpha_e(t_1) = E_e/E_b(t_1)$ - elasticity modulus ratio of the e-th reinforcement row and the concrete matrix, at moment t_1 . In that way, proper stresses in reinforcement will become equal to:

$$\sigma_{eP} = \sigma_{e, \text{contr.}} - \sigma_e(t_1) + \alpha_e(t_1) \sigma_b(z_e, t_1). \quad (25)$$

Fig. 2. Stress state of the beam element: a) with long-term service load; b) after unloading at the time moment t_1 ; c) after the application of P .

These same stresses can be presented in the following way:

$$\sigma_{eP} = \sigma_{e, \text{contr.}} - \sigma_{\text{loss}2e}(t_1), \quad (26)$$

where $\sigma_{\text{loss}2e}(t_1)$ - prestressing losses of the e -th reinforcement row at the application moment of the effort P . By equating expressions (25) and (26) we have obtained the formula for the evaluation of the generalized losses:

$$\sigma_{\text{loss}2e}(t_1) = \sigma_e(t_1) - \alpha_e(t_1) \sigma_b(z_e, t_1). \quad (27)$$

Thus, for the determination of prestressing losses in any e -th reinforcement row of the composite element, it is necessary to know the current initial stresses in the reinforcement and in the concrete matrix at the level of the same row, provoked by all of the long-term influences on the beams. These said current initial stresses can be evaluated by creep computation of the beams, detailed in [1, 2, 4]. The conditional effort P which can generalize the effect of proper stresses and the eccentricity of its application e_{0P} can be evaluated by following formulas:

$$P = (\sigma_{e, \text{contr.}} - \sigma_{\text{loss}2e}) A_e; e_{0P} = [(\sigma_{e, \text{contr.}} - \sigma_{\text{loss}2e}) A_e z_e] / P, \quad (28)$$

where A_e - section area of e -th reinforcement row.

At the end, have been realized the following phases of the computation:

- the composite beams have been reinforced according to the conditions of stiffness and durability of normal sections, taking into account the total value of the loading;
- according to the conditions of the prestressing, of the concrete matrix shrinkage, of the long-term loads, have been determined the current stresses in the matrix and in the reinforcement;
- by formula (27) have been evaluated the prestressing losses in the all reinforcement rows, and by the formulas (28) - the parameters $P(t)$ and $e_{0P}(t)$;
- by the formulas of Ukraine Codes of reinforced concrete structures 1.03.01-84 [3] has been proceeded the control of the beams according to the conditions of II group of limit states.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM AND TESTING RESULTS

Basic Material Properties

The programme consisted of casting twelve 180x100x1800 mm post-tensioned steel-concrete composite beams (Fig.3) with specified characteristic material properties of 40 MPa for the concrete matrix and $E_{SP} = 190.5$ GPa for the high-yield steel tendons.

Has been used 1 m³ of ready-mixed concrete matrix which was made from 430 kg of high early-strengthened Portland cement with activity of 50 MPa; 550 kg of quartz sand from Dniepr river with fineness modulus of 1,42; 1120 kg of granite crushed aggregate with particle size of 5-20 mm; 194 litres of water (water/cement ratio = 0,45); and 2,15 kg of alcohol formiate plasticiser. The said high-yield steel tendons with nominal diameters of 14 mm and 18 mm were contained in frames made of 5 mm bent mild steel mesh with $E_S = 171$ GPa.

The concrete matrix properties were determined by testing 43 (number of) 100x100x400 mm prisms (based on currently used Soviet Codes [3]) and 45 (number of) 100 mm cubes. The composite beams were prestressed to a target design force of 95 kN, after curing for 9 days.

Fig.3: Constructive schema of experimental model of steel-concrete composite beams.

Flexural, creep, shrinkage experiments and test results

At the concrete matrix age of 9 days, all of the composite beams were pressed out by prestressing efforts and then have been taken away from the prestressing bench together with their deflection indicators. 6 composite beams cast with prestressed reinforcement tendons diameter 14 mm were marked B₁ (table 1) and 6 other cast with diameter 18 mm - B₂.

Table 1. Computation exponents of the limit states of the beams

Beam series	σ_{SP} initial, MPa	A_{SP} , cm ²	Stress losses, MPa	σ_{SP} , residual, MPa	P, kN	e_{0P} , cm	ξ_R	ξ	M_u , kN.m	M_{crc} , kN.m
B ₁	617,3	1,54	88,9	528,4	75,77	3,6	0,44	0,36	13,1	8,9
B ₂	373,3	2,54	87,0	286,3	67,41	3,5	0,38	0,60	15,2	8,1

Two of the beams B₁ and two of B₂ conformably marked and , after their pressing out by the prestressing efforts were maintained in the laboratory without long-term loads. By them have been obtained the variations of the deformations in the prestressed tendons and in the concrete matrix, due to prestressing efforts and shrinkage of the concrete matrix.

Further, at the concrete matrix age of 76 days, 2 beams marked σ_{sp} and 2 marked σ_{sp} have been tested under long-term statical forces $F = 12$ kN (fig. 4).

Fig.4: Experimental graphics of time-dependent stresses in the prestressed reinforcement of the beam series: 1- σ_{sp} , 2- σ_{sp} and 3- σ_{sp} ; here theoretical graphics are with dotted lines.

At the same matrix age of 76 days, 2 composite beams marked σ_{sp} and 2 marked σ_{sp} have been tested also under long-term statical forces conformably $F = 22,5$ kN and $F = 20$ kN. (Fig. 5) Here the superscripts of the beams' series show the double of the statical forces' values. At the concrete matrix age of 378 days, all of the beams were tested under statical short-term successive loads up to their failure state [1, 2, 4].

Fig.5: Experimental graphics of time-dependent stresses in the prestressed reinforcement of the beam series: 1 - σ_{sp} ; 2 - σ_{sp} and 3 - σ_{sp} ; here theoretical graphics are with dotted lines.

All of these tests were carried out according to Soviet Codes of reinforced concrete structures 1.03.01.-84. [3]. Theoretical data of deformations in the concrete at upper facet of beams ϵ_b , increases of deformations in the prestressed reinforcement tendons $\Delta\epsilon_{sp}$ and the flexures of beams Δ , calculated by finite-difference method with step $h = 0,3$, then the experimental data of the same characteristics of the beams, obtained by their deflection indicators are presented in table 2. They show a satisfactory coincidence of theoretical and experimental data [1, 2, 4].

In table 3 have been presented theoretical and experimental data of limit states exponents of beams, calculated by formulas according to Ukraine standards and rules of reinforced concrete structures 1.03.01.-84 [3], taking into consideration the values of parameters $P(378)$ and $e_{op}(378)$, at the concrete age of 378 days obtained by formulas (28). Here the experimental data have been obtained by the testing of the beams under short-term successive loads up to their failure state. These said data confirm the positive effect of the long-term loads influences on the limit states exponents of beams M_{cr} and M_u .

Table 2: Theoretical (numerator) and experimental (denominator) characteristics of the beams' deformation state

Series of beams	τ , days	φ	$\epsilon_b \cdot 10^5$	$\Delta\epsilon_{SP} \cdot 10^5$	Δ , mm	Series of beams	$\epsilon_b \cdot 10^5$	$\Delta\epsilon_{SP} \cdot 10^5$	Δ , mm	
	9	0	-4,186	21,253	-0,66		-0,014	20,382	-0,63	
			-4,164	21,169	-0,61		-0,011	20,334	-0,59	
	24	0,6	-0,813	37,708	-0,99		-0,415	35,639	-0,93	
			-0,721	37,360	-0,87		-0,372	35,568	-0,83	
	76	1,2	12,149	61,965	-1,28		12,891	58,055	-1,10	
			12,010	61,884	-1,06		12,722	57,913	-1,02	
	378	1,8	30,261	94,515	-1,65		31,631	87,125	-1,35	
			30,023	94,281	-1,54		31,205	86,972	-1,25	
	76	0	40,211	50,144	-0,41		40,870	46,656	-0,30	
			40,081	50,016	-0,39		40,120	46,320	-0,29	
		118	0,6	69,417	66,651		-0,17	70,399	61,367	0,00
				68,640	66,305		-0,15	69,820	60,990	0,00
378		1,2	94,347	79,340	0,09	95,480	72,100	0,29		
			93,221	79,000	0,08	93,990	71,050	0,28		
76	0	43,683	85,381	2,64	41,695	45,966	1,75			
		42,840	85,168	2,53	41,480	45,670	1,58			
	118	0,6	78,602	133,82	4,42	74,195	74,972	3,07		
			78,030	133,68	4,22	74,00	74,740	2,85		
	378	1,2	111,00	181,01	6,08	104,20	103,49	4,30		
			109,85	179,85	5,87	102,50	102,50	4,02		

Table 3: Theoretical (numerator) and experimental exponents of beams' limit states

Series of beams	P, kN	e_{OP} , cm	$M_{cr,c}$, kN.cm	ξ	ξ_R	M_u , kN.cm	$a_{cr,c}$, mm
	70,53	- 3,19	1004	0,345	0,338	2661	-
			1050			2555	
	76,86	- 4,59	1151	0,348	0,338	2661	-
			1375			2529	
	128,84	- 3,68	-	0,386	0,338	2661	0,12
	60,26	- 3,01	941	0,391	0,373	3092	-
			985			3075	
	67,26	- 4,58	1089	0,394	0,400	3214	-
			1200			3248	
	135,60	- 4,53	-	0,459	0,382	3159	0,05
						3135	

Parallel to all these testings of the composite beams, have been tested at different concrete matrix ages of 9, 12, 15, 24, 36, 76, 118, 192, 208 and 378 days, concrete matrix prisms and cubes (3 prisms and 3 cubes at each said concrete matrix age) for the determination of the concrete matrix physical properties, and for the evaluation of the creep and shrinkage behaviour of the concrete matrix [1, 2, 4]. The creep and shrinkage tests were conducted in a

drying laboratory controlled at constant temperature ($23 \pm 0,5^{\circ}\text{C}$) and constant humidity [$50 \pm 2\%$ relative humidity (RH)], using standard $10 \times 10 \times 40$ cm prismatical specimens.

The test standard indicators (for shrinkage - $1/1000$; for creep - $1/100$) were used to measure the creep and shrinkage strains at selected time intervals. The tested creep specimens were marked

; here the superscripts of the prisms' series show the statical stresses' values in MPa, and their subscripts show the different concrete ages. During these creep tests, the specimens were mounted on the loading frame which consisted of a hydraulic jack, a load cell, and a system of coil springs held in compression by a set of rods and plates.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Theoretical values of crack moments M_{cr} of beams exceeded the same values of beams

by $14,6\%$, but for the experimental data this exceeding have reached $30,9\%$. Also the same comparison with beams and shows the exceeding of theoretical data by $15,7\%$ and the experimental data by $21,8\%$. Concerning the comparison of failure moments M_u , so, beams reinforced with prestressed tendons diameter 14 mm have shown almost the same bearing capacity. But the beams reinforced with tendons diameter 18 mm loaded under long-term statical forces have shown bearing capacity more higher by $2,2-5,6\%$ than those beams maintained in the laboratory without long-term loads [1, 2, 4].

2. These comparisons have shown that the nonlinear theory described in this report, is quite adequate and can be served for practical use. Experimental results have indicated that the finite-difference method based on the displacement formulation is suitable and effective to solve systems of nonlinear equilibrium differential equations. The consideration of this proposed design and experimental model, and these said time-dependent effects can be able to ensure interdependence of design and construction for economy of reinforcement up to $5\% - 15\%$.

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